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Research Article

**RELATIONSHIP OF HIGH TRIGLYCERIDE AND
CHOLESTEROL LEVEL IN PATIENTS WITH
HYPERTENSION, DIABETES AND CEREBROVASCULAR
ACCIDENTS****Dr Hannan Raza Khan¹, Dr Aziz Anwar Saleem², Dr Naima Hussain³**¹ Medical Officer, Govt General Hospital, Ghulam Muhammad Abad, Faisalabad² Medical Officer in Rural Health Center Satiana. Tehsil Jaranwala. District Faisalabad³ House Officer, Allied Hospital, Faisalabad**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To assess the prevalence of high cholesterol and triglycerides in patients with diabetes, hypertension and stroke.**Place and Duration:** In the Medicine department of Govt General Hospital, Ghulam Muhammad Abad, Faisalabad for one-year duration from January 2019 to January 2020.**Methods:** A total of 150 patients were selected from the medicine department after randomized sampling technique.**Results:** Isolated stroke was found in 93 (62%) of 150 patients and isolated diabetes in 57 (38%). Isolated hypertension was found in 21(7%), 6(2%) patients showed combined hypertension, CVA and diabetes mellitus. Combined hypertension and stroke were observed in 18 (6%) patients. Diabetes and hypertension were combined in 20 (6.7%) patients, and diabetes and stroke in 7 (2.3%) patients.**Key words:** diabetes, hypertension, stroke.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Hannan Raza Khan,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Cholesterol is an oily substance that thickens and narrows arterioles over the years. It is produced in the liver and is an essential element of blood¹⁻³. It is rich in egg yolks, butter, cream, animal fat and milk. Hypertensive retinopathy is a vascular complication of primary hypertension⁴⁻⁶. It is known that self-regulation of retinal circulation fails because blood pressure rises above a critical value. However, this does not fully explain the very degree of hypertensive retinopathy⁷⁻⁸. There are various risk factors such as age, gender, family trends, race and ethnic groups, as well as modifiable factors such as hypertension, heart disease, diabetes, dyslipidemia, smoking, alcohol abuse, and inactivity. physical, asymptomatic carotid stenosis and transient ischemic attacks. Stroke risk factors have been investigated locally. Serum lipids and the relationship of lipoproteins to cerebrovascular disease are studied with many other risk factors such as ischemic heart disease. Several clinical studies have shown a link between high serum cholesterol and ischemic stroke. The main risk factors that contribute to excessive cardiovascular disease caused by diabetes are hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, hypertension and smoking⁹⁻¹⁰.

It is known that dyslipidemia is a predisposing risk factor, an aggravating or complex factor in patients with hypertension. Hypertension and hyperlipidemia not only accelerate atherosclerosis, but also cause degenerative changes in the walls of

the large and middle arteries that accelerate cerebral bleeding, ischemic heart disease, stroke and cardiac arrest. High serum cholesterol levels have been observed in people suffering from non-hemorrhagic stroke, but not people suffering from intracranial or spinal hemorrhage. Serum lipids are thought to interact with the pathogenesis of non-hemorrhagic stroke through atherosclerosis.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The study was conducted at the Medicine department Govt General Hospital, Ghulam Muhammad Abad, Faisalabad for one year duration from January 2019 to January 2020. A total of 150 patients were selected from the medicine department after randomized sampling technique.

RESULTS:

Of the 150 patients, 76 (50.7%) were men and 74 (49.3%) were women. Regarding dyslipidemia in CVA, Hypertriglyceridaemia occurred in 18 (46%) men and 21 (54%) in women, while hypercholesterolemia was observed in 9 (60%) men and 6 (40%) in women. Dyslipidemia in hypertensive patients, hypertriglyceridaemia occurred in 12 (67%) men and 6 (33%) in women, and hypercholesterolemia was observed in 6 (67%) men and 3 (33%) in women. Dyslipidemia in diabetic patients, hypertriglyceridaemia occurred in 15 (38%) men and 24 (68%) in women, hypercholesterolemia was observed in 12 (50%) men and 12 (50%) in women.

Table 1: Triglycerides and cholesterol level in CVA (n=300 with CVA 48)

Age (yrs)	Male	Female
< 40	05	05
41-50	04	04
51-60	13	07
61-70	03	05
>70	02	-
Total	27	21

Table 2: Triglycerides and cholesterol level in patients with hypertension (n=300 with hypertension 23)

Age (yrs)	Male	Female
< 40	04	02
41-50	-	-
51-60	05	03
61-70	02	05
>70	02	-
Total	13	10

Table 3: Triglycerides and cholesterol level in patients with diabetes (n=300 with diabetes 60)

Age (yrs)	Male	Female
< 40	18	06
41-50	05	03
51-60	14	08
61-70	04	02
>70	-	-
Total	41	19

DISCUSSION:

Stroke is a clinical syndrome characterized by over 24 hours of symptoms and / or rapid development of focal and sometimes global symptoms of brain dysfunction. vascular origin. According to a 2002 World Health Organization report, total stroke mortality in Pakistan was 78,512, in this study 60 (36.4%) of 150 patients with a mean age of 54 years had diabetes isolated. 45% of these 60 patients are men and 55% are women¹¹. In this study, 21% of patients had an increase in serum cholesterol and 34.2% of patients had an increase in triglyceride levels (> 150 mg / dl). When we compared this study with one study, it was found that 24% of the population smokes cigarettes and 64% of patients lead a sedentary lifestyle¹². Another study showed that HMG reductase inhibitors were evaluated in 50 patients with dyslipidemia in patients with diabetes from Lahore. Total cholesterol and triglyceride levels were high in this study¹³. The total cholesterol and triglyceride levels in this study are very low compared to the current study. The reason is the financial situation, the difference between the inhabitants of Lahore and our region. Hyperglyperidemia is the most common lipid abnormality in NIDDM, especially in diabetic patients with poor glycemic control. The above observation was also observed in this study. Triglyceride levels were above the desired level in 34.2% of 60 patients, and the average triglyceride levels were below 150 mg / dl. Hypercyclidemia is a strong risk factor for macrovascular disease, which leads to impaired clearance of LDL, cholymicron and VLDL residues due to reduced insulin-dependent lipoprotein lipase synthesis in the liver¹³⁻¹⁴. High triglyceride levels are associated with hypercoagulopathy and reduced fibrinolysis, which contributes to coronary heart disease. In addition to the metabolic relationship with LDL cholesterol, it changes its particle into a denser, smaller, and therefore more atherogenic form. In this study, 23 (15.3%) patients with a mean age of 63 years were isolated patients with hypertension¹⁵. While 57% of them were men, 43% had elevated triglyceride levels. 32% of these patients smoked. Similar studies showed that 16% of patients had hyperglyceridaemia and 5% had high triglycerides and cholesterol.

CONCLUSION:

In our study, cholesterol and triglyceride levels increased in more patients. The exact cause of elevated cholesterol and triglycerides in this study is unknown. The study showed that 48% of patients had hypercholesterolemia. Another study showed that 50% of patients had dyslipidemia and 39% had hypertriglyceridaemia.

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